

3rd International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

Interreligious and Intercultural Action Research for Environmental Care: Crises, Wisdom, and Action

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ABSTRACT

This action research addressed the problem according to which pure research merely focuses on the theoretical and not acting directly on the practical. The aim of this paper was threefold: 1) to discuss three major crises confronting the community under study, 2) to analyze the wisdom from the different religions that frame the action of their devotees, and 3) to describe the social intervention of people of different cultures and religions to deal with these tripartite concerns. The literature reviewed included comparing and contrasting pure research, applied research, and action research, which led to development of a taxonomy of different types of action research. Qualitative data were collected through document analysis, community dialogue, and participant observation in an intercultural and interreligious tree-planting program. Yielding concrete intercultural and interreligious harmony through a concrete project, this research recommends academics to engage in action research to link theory with practice as well as promote social change and solve social problems.

Keywords: Action Research, Climate Crisis, Interfaith Dialogue, Religious Intolerance, Social Justice

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

This article zeroed in and discussed both theoretical and social problems. Theoretically, many research papers systematically review literature, dissect case studies, and provide recommendations for policies and further research. The problem is they stay on the realm of thinking and talking, there is no direct link between scientific observation and social action. In the same token, many activists protest for change, but are neither directly involved in concrete action for change nor involved in entering into dialogue with theories. Thus, theory and practice diverge. In the social context, the world is confronted with multifaceted problems: social injustice, religious intolerance, health crisis, and the climate crisis. Specifically, these concerns include very few rich controls the vast majority of global wealth, the COVID-19 pandemic, identity politics, and culture wars. Many of the research on these issues remains on the level of theories or technical investigation, leaving a wide gap for action for social change. Thus, this paper reflected on the what could be done and the ways in which these problems were concretely addressed in one case. By engaging in action research, this paper filled the gap that linked theory, reflection, and practice. See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Filling the Gap

Research Questions

This paper responded to these questions:

1. What are some of the major crises with which the world is confronted today?
2. What do the scriptures of the different religion reveal about caring for nature and society?
3. What action have interreligious and intercultural folks in a community undertaken to deal with these crises, based on their scriptural creeds?

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this paper was tripartite, namely to discuss the key crises that burdens the world today, to analyze the wisdom from different faith traditions about human cohesion and environmental care, and to describe the collaboration of people of different cultures and religions in an environmental project.

Contributions of the Study

Past social research about environmentalism, the climate crisis, and environmental crisis stayed only on the realm of ideas, theories, and policy recommendations for others to implement. Thus, there was no direct link between theory and practice in those research work. On the one hand, many researchers conduct pure research but were not engaged in action. On the other hand, social activists protest for social change but many were not involved in social change themselves. Hence, we see a bifurcation of theory and practice. This community participatory action research directly links theory (research findings about global crises) with practice (actually being directly involved in a community action).

Scope, Limitation, and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of this paper was interreligious and intercultural collaboration. It was limited to one project in northern Thailand. It did not deal with other collaborations. See Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Coverage of the Study

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theory used in this article was community participatory action research (CPAR). The operational indicators of community here were the cultural and faith representatives. Participation was manifested through involvement in a project. Action relates to planting trees together. Research engagement involved planning, writing, presentation and publication. See Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Community Participatory Action Research

Definition of Terms

Key words used in this paper included culture, intercultural, social justice, social injustice, religion, interreligious, environmental care, community, participatory, action, and research. Conceptual definition and operational definition were provided here. See Table 1 below:

Table 1: Definition of Terms

Terms	Conceptual Definition	Operational Definition
Culture (Ty, Glowacki-	Ethnicity, Gender, Nationality, Social Status, Age, etc.	Central Thai, Minorities, China, Eritrea, Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, S.

Dudka, & Berger, 2012)		Korea, UK, USA, Vietnam, Female, Male, Young, Old
Inter-cultural	Relations among different cultures	Relations among the above
Social Justice (Ty, 2010)	Treat everyone fairly without discrimination (Ty et al., 2012)	Treat everyone fairly regardless of economic, cultural, social, political, or other differences
Social Injustice	Not treat everyone fairly	Discriminate against others due to economic, cultural, social, political, or other differences
Religion (Ty, 2021a)	System of organized faith or opposition to it	Agnosticism, Baha'i, Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism, Sikhism, Traditional Religions
Inter-religious	Relations among diff religions	Relations among the above
Environmental Care (Ty, 2020)	Promotion of protection of Nature and sustainability	Tree planting, water conservation
Community	A group of people with common features	Cultural groups and faith-based groups
Participatory	To be engaged in activities together	Brainstorming, planning, dialogue, sharing ideas together
Action	To do something	Tree Planting
Research	To propose, write, and publish	Peer review, article presentation and publication

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provided an overview of the existing knowledge about pure research, applied research, and action research. It analyzed, critiqued, and synthesized the literature by providing a taxonomy. Traditional or pure research in such fields as biology, chemistry, humanities, physics, or sociology is either theory led or theory producing. Applied research in such fields as accounting, aerospace, dentistry, engineering, medicine, nursing, and social work is engaged in technical application of skills. Action research is engaged in the improvement of social context or practice, such as in the classroom, a community, or a country. See Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Three Major Types of Research

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This action research utilized the qualitative design, using the case study approach. The research site is a prominent city in northern Thailand. The population included the different religious communities and a university. Using purposive, convenience, and snowball sampling methods, one group of participants of this research included religious representatives with whom the researcher has been collaborating for the past five years. The second group of participants included two instructors in an undergraduate general elective class and their students. All participants of this action research come from different parts of the world: Africa (Eritrea), Asia (China, Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, South Korea, Thailand, Vietnam), Oceania (Australia), Latin America (Brazil), Europe (Belgium, Germany, U.K.), and North America (U.S.A.). Participants belonged to diverse cultural groups, including differences in citizenship, class, gender, majority-minority status, and other differences. The issues raised on the global level of analysis, such as economic crisis, social injustice, religious intolerance, and health crisis, all of which trickle down to the local community level of analysis. For this reason, action needs to be undertaken at the local level for social change. See Figure 5 below:

Figure 5: From Global to Local Levels of Analysis

Under the tutelage of the Institute for Advanced Study in Asian Cultures and Theologies 2021 (IASACT) of the Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK) which the United Board for Christian Higher Education in Asia (UB) supported, this research commenced in August and ended in December 2021. Research data collection methods included document analysis for research

question one, while data gathering methods for research questions two and three included participant observation, dialogue, and community action. For descriptive data analysis, the narrative discourses of religious representatives were coded. See Figure 6 below:

Figure 6: Methodology

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Crises

This section responded to the first research question: What are some of the major crises with which the world is confronted today? Some of the major problems facing the world today include, among others, economic crisis and social injustice, religious intolerance, climate crisis, the threat of nuclear annihilation, and the health crisis. This article focuses on only four of these major issues for the purpose of this specific community participatory action research.

Economic Crisis and Social Injustice. The first crisis this paper identified involves economic crisis and social injustice. The global economic crisis under corporate globalization that the majority of the people are experiencing today reveals the class struggle from above between the 1% and the rest of society. Social injustice thrives (Ty, 2011b), as the world is experiencing a deepening economic crisis today (Ty & Alkarzon, 2014), which the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbates (Baldwin, Weder, & Centre for Economic Policy Research (Great Britain), 2020). The pandemic further enriched the already super rich (Reich, 2020). Workers, including migrant workers were the hardest hit during the pandemic. Losing their jobs, the unemployed does not have any income to ensure food security in such a prolonged emergency situation which lasts for years on end (Mottaleb, Mainuddin, & Sonobe, 2020). The rich get richer, as wealth accumulates to the top one-percent billionaires who pretend to be virtuous and magnanimous through philanthro-capitalism (Berkeley Economic Review Staff, 2020). There is a growing movement calling for non-payment of debt which are immoral due to the corrupt financial system which syphons money upwards through the so-called socialism for the rich and capitalism for the rest of us (Collective Debt, 2020).

The economy, politics, and culture in society are symbiotically intertwined. The economic crisis laid bare the stark racism and prejudices of late-stage capitalism. Instead of looking at corporate globalization straight in the eye as the culprit, foreigners and migrant workers became the

scapegoat of decreasing income and opportunities. The working class, labor unions, and the classical social movement were responsible for gains in the policy formulation and implementation of eight-hour working days, weekends off work, minimum wage, paid leave, paid holidays, healthcare, and pension plans in many parts of the world. However, the middle class, intellectuals, and liberal-minded elite turned their backs on the class struggle of the working class for the continuing amelioration of the condition.

Dropping class struggle, the middle class in the advanced capitalist states formed part of what is known as the new social movement, focusing their energy on matters such as gender, sexuality, color, race, ethnicity, culture, religion, and other differences tagged as postmodernism and identity politics (Ty, Daniels, & Pongo, 2010). By narrowing their concerns on atomistic issues and micro narratives, the adherents of postmodernism and identity politics pitted one against the other, leaving the monopoly capitalists triumphant (Sison, 2021a). Rather than focusing on individual differences, collectively, we need to struggle for a better future for all of humanity (Krugman, 2020). We need to see human beings in our integrity: each person embodies a social class, gender, color, ethnicity, culture, and so on. Thus, we cannot separate class struggle from our struggle for social, economic, and racial justice. The grassroots working together can change the rules so that we can create a new economy beyond capitalism that benefits the majority of the people (New Economics Foundation, 2020). See Figure 7 below:

Figure 7: From Social Injustice to Social Justice in Economic and Other Identities

Religious Intolerance. The second crisis this paper identified was religious intolerance. Asia is home to several world religions and traditional religions. Religious pluralism provides diversity, which is both a virtue and a vice. It is a virtue, as Asians are able to experience the richness of its religious heritage. However, it is also a vice, given that there is widespread religious intolerance which could lead to prejudice, persecution, kidnapping, forced marriages, communal violence, and genocide.

In Bangladesh, religious extremists attack Hindus and Christians (Ty, 2017a). In India, the upper caste exploit the lowest caste by making them engage in the illegal manual scavenging, which is the use of women’s hands to collect human excrements in public toilets and men to dunk and work in clogged sewage (Christian Conference of Asia, 2017). In Myanmar, the security forces attacked majority Muslim Rohingya in the villages in which survivors embarked on a forced exodus to neighboring Bangladesh to seek a refuge and sanctuary (Ty, 2019). In Pakistan, Christian

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neighborhoods were bombed, women forced into marriage, and non-Muslims are easily charged with the anti-blasphemy laws (Ty, 2017c).

In West Papua, the indigenous Papuan people are harassed or attacked by the Indonesian security forces, leading to flagrant violations of human rights (Ty, 2017b). Feudal lords, comprador bourgeoisie, and bureaucrat capitalists (Sison, 1970) from the north who settled in the southern Philippines not only extracted wealth but also discriminated the indigenous peoples and Muslims (Russell & Ty, 2010; Ty, 2011b, 2011a). In this case, economic exploitation is hidden in the guise of the postmodern identity politics of religion and culture, which misses the point of the significance of the economic structure of society (Sison, 2021a).

Health Crisis. The third crisis with which this paper is concerned was the health crisis. Since December of 2019, the world is faced with the COVID-19 virus. By early 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the coronavirus a global pandemic (World Health Organization, 2021). The right to health of the majority of the world's population was at stake amidst the pandemic (Christian Conference of Asia CCA, 2020). As companies, factories, and shops closed, workers lost their jobs. As unemployment increases, more and more people do not have any source of income to provide for the roof of their families and food at the table. Clearly, poverty and food security during the pandemic are directed related (M & Am, 2020). COVID-19 has brought about economic losses as well as food insecurity (Mottaleb et al., 2020). COVID-19 has specifically hurt the food security in Asia where countless people live under the poverty line (Caballero-Anthony, Teng, & Montesclaros, 2020).

As workplaces closed and as workers lose their jobs, husbands, wives, and partners stay at home 24/7, which causes the increased possibilities of family troubles and tensions. Studies show the gendered impact of the pandemic, as violence against women has increased during the time of the pandemic, for which reason gender sensitive services are necessary (CCA, 2020). Violence against women also increased in border crossings, as most of the security forces and border patrols not only abused their powers but also did not have training on gender sensitivity when conducting security checks.

Now, practically everyone on Earth has to observe common protocols to stop or avoid the spread of the virus. These measures include social distancing, wearing face masks, washing hands regularly, as well as vaccination against the virus. Unfortunately, two problems arise. One, the anti-science anti-vax movement is on the rise, thanks to the power of the social media (Mylan & Hardman, 2021). Two, rich countries are practicing vaccine nationalism (Hutschman, 2021). The world will be safe from the virus, if everyone is vaccinated. Virus mutations shall continue if vaccine nationalism is not stopped (Eaton, 2021). Hence, there is a need for vaccine equity as the path forward to make the world safe again from the virus (Katz, Weintraub, Bekker, & Brandt, 2021).

A new world is possible. We can surmount the heavy structural constraints of the neoliberal economic model of corporate globalization. Many intellectuals have provided recommendations for a better world. Reich indicates that the already super rich benefited even more during the pandemic, while their workers have to sacrifice their health and lives for the corporate profits of

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billionaires (Reich, 2020). Varoufakis describes the current economic system as techno-fascism (Al Jazeera English, 2021). Far from wishing to return to normal prior to the pandemic, we must create a new system beyond capitalism (Varoufakis, 2020). To heal the world from the pandemic, Žižek even dared talk about communism, otherwise we will fall into barbarism (Žižek, 2020).

Climate Crisis. The fourth crisis with which this paper dealt was the climate crisis. In political economy, nature and society are interconnected (Ty, 2020). The climate crisis is at an emergency state so much so that governments hold global summits to discuss ways by which to deal with it. Klein indicated that capitalism is principally the culprit of the destruction of nature as well as the rise of the climate crisis (Klein, 2015). Capitalist plunder of nature for the sake of profit leads to what one author calls climate imperialism (Sison, 2021b).

Due to the climate crisis, many people are leaving their countries of origin to become migrant workers, as they cannot continue living in a subsistence economy (Sison, 2021c). One author calls our period in history as capitalocene (Moore, 2016). Clearly, the pandemic and climate crisis have a heavy toll on agriculture and food security (Rasul, 2021).

Workers realize that the economic crisis, health crisis, and the climate crisis have a negative impact on their well-being, for which reasons they need to bond together in siblinghood (Ty, 2021b). In summary, the struggle in our common home for economic justice, health justice, and climate justice are intertwined (Ty, 2020). As a response to the about crises, the author of this paper has described the preliminary output of a participatory action research on the care for water and life on earth in a previous article (Ty, 2021). To avert the climate crisis and catastrophe, we need to go beyond capitalism and work for a system change (Sison, 2021d).

Wisdom

This section responded to the second research question: What do the scriptures of the different religion reveal about caring for nature and society?

Contributions for the selection of wisdom from the different faith traditions came from religious representatives who attended the tree-planting program (Institute of Religion, Culture, and Peace Interreligious Tree-Planting Committee, 2021). Additional inputs came from reflections of students in two undergraduate classes who participated in the tree-planting project. In alphabetical order, these traditions included agnosticism, Baha'i, Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism, Sikhism, and Traditional Beliefs.

An agnostic stated that he did not need any religious reason for which to cares about nature. He simply realized that nature needs both respect and protection, regardless of one's religion. All life forms or living things need mutual respect.

Two Baha'i representatives attended the tree-planting event, one of whom was a Lanna Thai, while the other was an ethnic Karen. Both of them cited their prophet Baha'u'llah, indicating that nature if the will, revelation, and expression of God in this world. The Baha'i International Community agreed that nature must be valued and respected; thus, we must preserve the Earth's biodiversity.

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From the Buddhist representatives, we learned about the teaching of Metta Sutta or Loving Kindness, according to which we must do no harm to all sentient beings and live in harmony with the natural world as we are all interconnected.

Christian representatives cited the Holy Bible in their discussion about the need to take care of nature. Humans must seek reconciliation with the rest of creation. We need to engage in improving the plight of the poor and of the Earth to promote long-term sustainable peace based on justice, instead of promoting greed and profit.

In Hinduism, nature is respected so much so that it is called mother. Hindu priests neither cut trees, nor eat meat. They consider that trees have own lives and must therefore be respected. For Hinduism, nature is important: the earth is called Mother Earth, the Goddess Ganga is represented in water, Phra Varun symbolizes rain, Phra Phai represented wind, and Phra Agni represents fire.

The Muslim representatives in this even cited the Holy Qur'an, indicating that humans must "not desire corruption in the land. Indeed, God does not like corruptors" (Qur'an, 28:77). Moreover, the followers of Islam are told: "Devote thyself single-mindedly to the faith, and thus follow the nature designed by Allah, the nature according to which He has fashioned mankind; there is no altering the creation of Allah" (Qur'an, Surat Al-Roum).

In the Jewish Bible, we are told that "The Lord God took the man and put him in the garden of Eden to work it and keep it" (Genesis, 2:14). In relation to environmental protection and this tree-planting project, there are some important Biblical citations. "They will be like a tree planted by the water that sends out its roots by the stream. It does not fear when heat comes; its leaves are always green. It has no worries in a year of drought and never fails to bear fruit" (Jeremiah 17:18). Here is the second related passage: "And he shall be like a tree planted by the rivers of water, that bringeth forth his fruit in his season; his leaf also shall not wither; and whatsoever he doeth shall prosper" (Psalm 1 3:3).

For Sikhism, its followers are enjoined to take action against the climate crisis. Since 2011, its adherents in over two thousand Sikh organizations globally host an annual Sikh Environmental Day, during which they are engaged in environmental education, action, and reflection. EcoSikh, its Washington D.C.-based organization, is a signatory to the United Nations Interfaith Summit on Climate Change.

Those who believe in traditional religions, such as the Lisu of northern Thailand and in the bordering countries, are conservationists. They respect nature in their daily lives and honor their territorial guardian spirits when they interact with nature.

In summary, all of the above belief systems, both religious and non-religious, support the argument according to which the care for and protection of nature is intrinsic part of human responsibility, though expressed in different religious platitudes.

Community Action

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This section responded to the third research question: What action have interreligious and intercultural folks in a community undertaken to deal with these crises, based on their scriptural creeds?

An article about the conceptualization and pre-implementation progress of this tree-planting project was published earlier in 2021 (Ty, 2021). This article focused on the actual program of the tree-planting itself. On Monday, November 15, 2021, an interreligious and intercultural tree planting program took place on the grounds of the Department of Peacebuilding and the Institute of Religion, Culture, and Peace, on the main campus of Payap University. The event started at 2 PM and ended at around 4 pm. In this time of the pandemic, all health precautions were put in place: attendees put on face masks, had access to hand sanitizer and gloves, as well as maintained social distance.

The afternoon program included the following: opening ecumenical prayer, welcome remarks, cherry tree planting, chestnut tree planting, interreligious representatives' reflections of their scriptures on nature and environmental care, student reflections, student offering of plants to religious representatives and community members, group photos, refreshments, and fellowship.

The afternoon event started with Rev. Grace Moon of the Christian Conference of Asia (CCA), which is based in the Genesis (Pathomgarn) Building on campus, giving the opening ecumenical prayer. Ajarn Komgrit Wongnam, who represented Payap University President Ajan Apich Insuwan, gave the Welcome Remarks on behalf of the university president.

The participants of the event are very diverse in terms of religion, culture, national origins, and professions, among them were religious leaders, students, faculty, university administrators, staff, expats, and retirees. Religious representatives came from different faith traditions, including Baha'i, Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam, and Sikhism. There were an African (Eritrea), Americans (U.S.A.), Asians (China, Indonesia, Myanmar, Nepal, the Philippines, South Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam), Europeans (Belgium, Germany, and the U.K.), a Latin American (Brazil), and Pacific folks (Australia) in attendance.

After the welcome remarks, all the attendees went to the plot where the cherry sapling was planted. Each volunteer, of different religions, took turns in shoveling in some garden soil and peat moss onto the new plant. A Buddhist monk and a Muslim imam shared in the planting efforts, as well as a British Anglican priest and a female Thai Hindu monk. The next tree that was planted was a walnut sapling. People of different faiths took turns in shoveling in some garden soil and peat moss onto the walnut sapling. Religious leaders, faculty, staff, and students took turns to shovel some garden soil and sprinkled water on the newly planted saplings.

Thereafter, the religious representatives sat on the presidential table from which each one gave a thoughtful reflection from their own Holy Books about the importance of nature and the environment as well as environmental care and the relationship of human beings with the natural world. The participants of the event heard words of wisdom from different Scriptures about caring for the natural world. The readings from the sacred texts were followed by students offering plants to each representative of the different faith traditions as a symbol of spreading the knowledge,

skills, and values of environmentalism to every corner, every culture, and every religion. The original plan was to have a tree planting event in different sites; however, the pandemic changed all that. Group photos were taken after the gift giving.

Afternoon refreshments composed of Thai food, Indian food, Thai coconut and rice desserts, and assorted Thai iced tea drinks were served. In a display of empathetic fellowship, people of different cultures, faiths, and professions mingled when they broke bread together, informally learning from each other about each other, regardless of religion, sex, culture, national origin, and other differences.

The summary of the paper is encapsulated in the following Figure 8 below:

Figure 8: Summary of the Paper

SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND CONCLUSION

Summary

First Research Question. To paraphrase, what are the major crises with which the world is confronted today? The responses included economic crisis and economic injustice, religious intolerance, health crisis, and climate crisis.

Second Research Question. In so many words, what are some of the wisdoms from the different religions about environmental care? Wisdoms were derived through dialogue from agnosticism, Baha’i, Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism, Sikhism, and Traditional Beliefs, all of which promote living in harmony with as well as taking care of nature.

Third Research Question. In a nutshell, what action have interreligious and intercultural folks in a community undertaken to deal with these crises, based on their scriptures? This paper presented a case study of a community participatory action research involving the planting of a cherry tree and a chestnut tree in northern Thailand. The outcomes of this community participatory action research included intercultural collaboration, interreligious harmony, and climate justice at the local level. See Figure 9 below:

Figure 9: Grounded Theory of the Community Participatory Action Research

Recommendations

This action research reveals that intellectuals and religious leaders do not only have to be concerned about the environmental crisis, but also that they can be actually involved in engaging some concrete actions that promote environmentalism and protect nature. Thus, researchers must not only recommend others to be engaged in social change but they themselves can be involved in social transformation and become the agents of change themselves.

In Conclusion

This article examined the crises that affect humanity today, share the wisdom from different faith traditions that call for environmental care, as well as depict the community participatory action research involving a tree-planting project as a case study of environmental care in action.

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